

Instrument 1 (Model)

Name: _____ Date: _____
Course: _____ Start time: _____
Enrollment: _____ End time: _____

1. The goal is to develop a data model for a veterinary hospital. Customers and veterinarians are people who need to have their data persisted. Customers have contact information like phone and email. Veterinarians have a record of their admission to the clinic, as well as their salary. Each client can own one or more animals, and these can be treated. To perform each treatment, it is necessary to know the age and size of the animal. The treatment has a predicted duration, a specific value and also involves the use of medicines that are noted in the prescriptions. Each animal may be suffering from one or more diseases, with the most varied names and possible causes. The simplest occurrences of treatments are usually resolved by a single veterinarian, however, there may be situations in which an animal is treated by more than one veterinarian. Eventually, a veterinarian may also have an assistant who, as a rule, is other veterinary.